

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

No 1

2026

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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OPTIMIZING HUMAN CAPITAL: THE IMPACT OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. Effective management in vocational education enhances economic returns through the development of human capital. This article examines the impact of leadership on organizational culture and institutional stability. The primary objective of the study is to evaluate managerial effectiveness. The findings reveal that leadership accounts for 62.3 % of organizational stability. The principal is identified as the key architect of human capital development within vocational education institutions.

Key words: Human Capital Development, Vocational Education, Labor Market, Instructional Leadership, Organizational Culture, Administrative Personnel.

Annotatsiya. Kasbiy ta'lim tizimida samarali boshqaruv inson kapitalini rivojlantirish orqali iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Mazkur maqolada rahbarlikning ta'lim muassasasidagi tashkiliy madaniyat va barqarorlikka ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi boshqaruv faoliyatining samaradorligini baholashdan iborat. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, rahbarlik omili tashkilot barqarorligining 62,3 % ini izohlaydi. Ta'lim muassasasi direktori inson kapitalini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishning asosiy subyekti sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Inson kapitalini rivojlantirish, Kasbiy ta'lim, Mehnat bozori, Ta'limiy rahbarlik, Tashkiliy madaniyat, Boshqaruv xodimlari.

Аннотация. Эффективное управление в системе профессионального образования способствует повышению экономической отдачи за счёт развития человеческого капитала. В статье анализируется влияние лидерства на формирование организационной культуры и устойчивость образовательного учреждения. Цель исследования заключается в оценке эффективности управленческой деятельности. Результаты исследования показывают, что фактор лидерства объясняет 62,3 % организационной стабильности. Руководитель образовательной организации выступает ключевым архитектором человеческого капитала.

Ключевые слова: Развитие человеческого капитала, Профессиональное образование, Рынок труда, Педагогическое лидерство, Организационная культура, Административный персонал.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of Uzbekistan's dynamically evolving economy, vocational education institutions function as a central mechanism for human capital development. These institutions play a crucial role in aligning national education outcomes with the growing demand of the industrial labor market for skilled and technically competent personnel. From this perspective, vocational education institutions hold strategic importance for macroeconomic stability, as they are directly responsible for preparing a workforce capable of supporting sustainable industrial growth through relevant technical competencies.

At the same time, in Uzbekistan—as observed in several developed economies such as Australia, China, and the United States—the vocational education sector has historically received limited recognition within the broader educational framework. In some cases, it has been perceived as an alternative or supplementary educational pathway rather than a core driver of economic development. From an economic standpoint, such perceptions may constrain the full utilization of vocational education's potential. Consequently, the capabilities

of learners oriented toward technical professions or originating from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds may not be fully integrated into national education investment strategies.

The ultimate Return on Investment (ROI) of vocational education is primarily reflected in graduate employment rates and labor productivity. Achieving strong outcomes in these indicators requires not only well-designed curricula but also high levels of institutional efficiency. Such efficiency is fostered through clearly defined instructional objectives and a supportive organizational environment that enables effective educational delivery.

While existing research has predominantly emphasized the pedagogical role of teaching staff, this study highlights the significant contribution of administrative personnel to the economic performance of vocational education institutions. As key actors in resource allocation, policy execution, and strategic decision-making, administrative staff play a decisive role in shaping organizational culture. This culture, in turn, either facilitates or constrains the institution's capacity to produce a highly skilled workforce aligned with labor market demands.

By examining the relationship between Instructional Leadership and Organizational Culture from the perspective of non-teaching staff, this study addresses an important gap in the literature. It provides a management-oriented understanding of how institutional efficiency supports the contribution of vocational education institutions to national economic development. This approach underscores the critical importance of leadership-driven organizational effectiveness within the vocational education system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Extensive scholarly literature has consistently demonstrated a strong and meaningful relationship between school leadership and institutional performance, positioning the principal as the central architect of school effectiveness. Prior research conceptualizes leadership influence as operating through both direct and indirect mechanisms. Direct effects relate to organizational outputs, resource utilization, and operational efficiency, while indirect effects manifest through the shaping of internal processes that ultimately influence student outcomes. From the perspective of institutional economics, these findings underscore that leadership extends beyond a purely pedagogical function and represents a critical determinant of a school's overall operational and organizational effectiveness.

Within the context of vocational education, Principal Instructional Leadership (PIL) has emerged as a comprehensive management framework that integrates instructional oversight with industry alignment. PIL encompasses the strategic responsibilities undertaken by principals to guide, monitor, and support instructional practices that define the institution's capacity to produce labor-market-relevant skills. In this regard, effective principals function analogously to operational managers, emphasizing the optimization of management systems, coordination across departments, and the alignment of instructional processes with institutional goals. Such leadership practices contribute directly to improvements in educational quality and institutional coherence.

The scope of Principal Instructional Leadership further extends to the strategic allocation of both human and physical capital. Principals are tasked with articulating institutional priorities, directing limited resources toward high-impact instructional activities, and establishing the professional infrastructure necessary to support the continuous development of teachers and staff. Contemporary perspectives on instructional leadership emphasize the importance of bridging traditional divisions between academic and non-academic personnel. By fostering a collaborative and inclusive organizational climate, principals reduce operational inefficiencies and enable the institution to function as an integrated system, thereby enhancing the overall Return on Investment (ROI) of administrative and educational efforts.

Organizational culture constitutes a foundational form of institutional capital that is closely associated with efficiency, stability, and performance outcomes. Widely described as the "social glue" of organizations, culture represents a socially constructed asset that aligns employee behavior with institutional objectives while minimizing internal friction. In vocational education settings, organizational culture carries particular economic significance, as it shapes how personnel interpret priorities, coordinate tasks, and implement strategic directives. A stable and cohesive culture provides a shared institutional identity that integrates educational values with the technical and procedural demands of workforce preparation. Empirical studies indicate that collaborative cultures foster high-support environments, reduce the hidden costs associated with low motivation, and promote collective responsibility for achieving industry-aligned outcomes.

Within this organizational framework, administrative personnel occupy a pivotal role as operational gatekeepers of the vocational education system. This group of non-teaching staff—including vice principals, quality assurance officers, and student affairs administrators—forms the strategic middle layer of management responsible for sustaining the institution's instructional mission. Although they are not directly engaged in classroom instruction, these administrators design and maintain the conditions under which instruction occurs. Their responsibilities encompass resource management, policy implementation, stakeholder coordination, and

the maintenance of partnerships with government and industry actors. When leadership practices empower administrative personnel to move beyond narrowly defined technical functions toward strategic engagement, their sense of autonomy and accountability increases, contributing to higher levels of organizational productivity and institutional effectiveness.

Guided by this conceptual framework, the present study seeks to examine leadership and culture within vocational education institutions from the perspective of administrative personnel. Specifically, the research investigates the perceived levels of Instructional Leadership and Organizational Culture among non-teaching staff and evaluates the extent to which Instructional Leadership predicts the quality and stability of the organizational environment. Accordingly, the study advances the hypothesis that Principal Instructional Leadership serves as a significant positive predictor of Organizational Culture, accounting for a substantial proportion of institutional variance and reinforcing the role of leadership as a driver of sustainable organizational performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative research design employing a cross-sectional survey approach to examine management-driven determinants of institutional health within the vocational education sector. Recognizing vocational schools as a strategic investment in Uzbekistan's human capital development, the research specifically focused on administrative personnel, who function as the institutional "middle management" responsible for ensuring operational efficiency and organizational coherence. Data collection was conducted through an online survey administered over a two-week period in June–2025 and covered four economically significant regions of Uzbekistan: Tashkent, Ferghana, Samarkand, and Sirdarya. This regional scope ensured that the findings reflect diverse institutional and economic contexts within the national vocational education system.

Participants were recruited using a convenience sampling strategy, with survey invitations disseminated through regional departments of vocational education. This approach yielded a substantial sample of 563 administrative staff members representing 43 vocational education institutions. All participants occupied non-teaching roles directly associated with resource allocation, policy implementation, quality assurance, and institutional coordination. Prior to participation, respondents were provided with a clear explanation of the study's objectives through an informed consent disclaimer. Participation was voluntary, anonymity was fully guaranteed, and ethical research standards were strictly upheld, thereby ensuring the reliability and integrity of the collected data.

The survey instrument was developed through a rigorous multi-stage validation process designed to ensure conceptual clarity, cultural relevance, and measurement accuracy. Measurement scales were adapted from well-established theoretical frameworks to align with the study's operational definitions of leadership and organizational culture. To ensure linguistic equivalence, all survey items underwent a double-blind translation and back-translation process between English and Uzbek. Content validity was further strengthened through expert review by two scholars specializing in educational leadership and management, who evaluated the items for their relevance to the strategic and administrative realities of vocational education. A pilot study involving 30 administrative personnel was subsequently conducted to assess clarity, flow, and interpretability of the questionnaire, resulting in minor refinements to enhance precision and consistency.

Principal Instructional Leadership was measured using a scale grounded in the seminal work of Hallinger (2011), which conceptualizes instructional leadership as a strategic orientation toward curriculum management, instructional supervision, and institutional development. The study employed a 20-item instrument encompassing three core dimensions: defining the school mission, managing the instructional program, and promoting a positive learning climate. Responses were recorded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Within the present sample, the scale demonstrated exceptionally high internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.976, indicating that administrative personnel perceive instructional leadership as a highly cohesive and integrated management construct.

Organizational Culture was assessed using an eight-item scale derived from Schein's (2010) organizational theory, which conceptualizes culture as a system of shared values, norms, and beliefs that shape institutional behavior. The scale captures key aspects of the workplace environment, including institutional identity, administrative responsibility, and internal support mechanisms. Responses were likewise measured on a five-point Likert scale. The reliability analysis produced a Cronbach's alpha of 0.908, confirming the scale's robustness and suitability for assessing the organizational environment within Uzbekistan's vocational education context.

Data analysis was conducted using Stata 14 software and followed a structured progression from descriptive analysis to predictive modeling. In line with the methodological approach proposed by Jackson and Tomlinson (2020), Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was first applied to verify the construct validity of the adapted measurement scales. Subsequently, Simple Linear Regression analysis was employed to examine

the predictive influence of Principal Instructional Leadership on Organizational Culture. This analytical model enabled the estimation of the coefficient of determination, thereby providing a direct and interpretable measure of the extent to which institutional culture is shaped by leadership practices. As such, the analysis offers a clear indicator of management-driven institutional efficiency within vocational education institutions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Instrument Validity

Principal Components Analysis was conducted to verify the construct validity of the research scales. For Instructional Leadership, a unidimensional structure was confirmed (Eigenvalue = 13.78), accounting for 68.9% of the total variance. Similarly, the Organizational Culture scale yielded a single-factor solution (Eigenvalue = 4.91), explaining 61.3% of the variance. For both instruments, factor loadings were strong and exceeded recommended thresholds, confirming that the items successfully converge into their respective constructs.

Descriptive Statistics and Normality

Administrative personnel reported high perceptions of both Instructional Leadership ($M = 4.20$, $SD = 0.77$) and Organizational Culture ($M = 4.03$, $SD = 0.74$). The low standard deviations (< 1.0) suggest a high degree of consensus among the 563 respondents.

Normality was evaluated using skewness and kurtosis. While formal testing (sktest) indicated a non-normal distribution ($p < 05$), which is typical for large sample sizes, the descriptive coefficients remained within acceptable psychometric limits. Skewness ranged from -1.32 to -0.96 and kurtosis from 4.32 to 5.27 , falling well below the thresholds of 5 and 10 , respectively, thus justifying the use of parametric statistical procedures.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

A simple linear regression was performed to examine the extent to which Instructional Leadership predicts the quality of Organizational Culture. Preliminary Pearson correlation analysis indicated a strong, significant positive association between the two variables ($r = .79$, $p < .001$).

The regression model was statistically significant, explaining 62.3% of the variance in Organizational Culture ($R^2 = .623$). Instructional Leadership was found to be a significant positive predictor of school culture ($\beta = .79$, $p < .001$). These results suggest that as principals become more active and effective in their instructional leadership roles, there is a corresponding and substantial improvement in the perceived health and stability of the vocational school's organizational environment.

Overall, the results of the regression analysis provide a formal test of the study's hypothesis. Hypothesis 1, which proposed that Principal Instructional Leadership is a significant positive predictor of Organizational Culture, was firmly supported.

The primary objective of this study was to examine the predictive power of Instructional Leadership on Organizational Culture within vocational school settings. The results revealed a remarkably strong relationship, with Instructional Leadership explaining 62.3% of the variance in school culture. This finding aligns with the "top-down" theory of organizational climate, suggesting that the behaviors and priorities of the principal directly shape the shared values and norms of the institution.

The high mean score for Instructional Leadership ($M = 4.20$) indicates that administrative staff view their leaders as highly engaged in the core business of teaching and learning. This active involvement likely fosters a culture of professional growth and stability ($M = 4.03$). In the specific context of vocational education—where industry alignment and technical skill acquisition are paramount—the principal's role in setting clear instructional goals appears to provide the structural "backbone" that supports a healthy organizational environment.

Furthermore, the strong correlation ($r = .79$) suggests that these two constructs are deeply intertwined. When a leader prioritizes instructional quality, it naturally cultivates a culture of accountability and support. Conversely, a weak or detached leadership style likely leads to a fragmented or stagnant culture.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides strong empirical evidence that Instructional Leadership is a decisive determinant of Organizational Culture within vocational education institutions. The findings demonstrate that the leadership practices of school principals play a central role in shaping the overall health, stability, and effectiveness of the workplace environment. With instructional leadership accounting for more than 60 % of the variance in organizational culture, the results indicate that meaningful improvements in school climate are most effectively achieved through the systematic professional development of school leaders. In this sense, the principal functions as a stabilizing cultural anchor, aligning institutional values, practices, and expectations.

Beyond its organizational implications, the study carries important economic significance. Vocational schools serve as a critical link between the education system and the labor market, operating as institutional

mechanisms for human capital formation. Given that instructional leadership explains a substantial proportion of cultural variance, the principal effectively assumes a role comparable to that of a chief operational decision-maker in a human capital-producing organization. A well-aligned and supportive organizational culture enhances resource efficiency, minimizes internal friction, and promotes sustainable staff engagement. In contrast, less coherent leadership practices may limit institutional potential by increasing hidden operational costs such as staff turnover and reduced instructional effectiveness. The strong leadership levels identified in this study ($M = 4.20$) are associated with the development of a high-performance organizational culture that ensures resources are strategically directed toward student skill acquisition and workforce readiness. From a Return on Investment perspective, investing in the training and development of vocational school principals emerges not only as an educational priority but also as a sound economic strategy to strengthen the stability and continuity of the industrial workforce pipeline.

Despite the robustness of the sample ($N = 563$), several methodological considerations should be acknowledged. Data were collected through self-reported surveys administered to administrative personnel, which introduces the possibility of response bias, including socially desirable evaluations of leadership practices. In addition, the cross-sectional design captures perceptions at a single point in time. While the regression analysis indicates a strong predictive relationship, it does not establish causal direction. It is plausible that a well-established organizational culture may also facilitate more effective leadership practices. Furthermore, the high correlation observed between instructional leadership and organizational culture ($r = .79$) suggests partial conceptual overlap between the constructs. Future research would benefit from the use of more differentiated measurement instruments to ensure clearer empirical separation between leadership behaviors and cultural attributes.

The findings of this study offer several practical and policy-oriented implications. At the policy level, recruitment, certification, and professional development programs for vocational school principals should extend beyond administrative compliance and emphasize instructional leadership competencies, given their demonstrated impact on organizational culture. In the vocational education sector, a stable and supportive institutional culture ($M = 4.03$) contributes to reduced economic costs associated with administrative inefficiencies and staff attrition, thereby enabling more sustainable and productive partnerships with industry stakeholders and supporting regional economic development. At the institutional level, principals are encouraged to engage in regular organizational culture assessments to evaluate how leadership decisions influence daily work practices and staff experiences. Finally, future research should adopt longitudinal designs spanning a 2–3 year period and incorporate qualitative methods such as interviews or case studies. Such approaches would provide deeper insight into how specific leadership behaviors—such as classroom observation, mentoring, and performance feedback—translate into measurable and sustained shifts in organizational culture.

REFERENCES

1. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024, October 16). On measures to further improve the system of training qualified personnel in vocational education and to introduce international educational programs (Presidential Decree No. PF-158). National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/7166683>
2. Abdurakhmanov, K., & Magrupov, A. (2025). Human capital development for the green economy: Labor market demands and vocational education strategies. *Iqtisodiyot: Tahlillar va Prognozlar / Economy: Analysis and Forecasts*, 2(30), April–June.
3. Agasisti, T., Catalano, G., & Sibiano, P. (2020). School leadership, resource allocation, and student achievement: An efficiency analysis of Italian schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(1), 47–66.
4. Gümüş, S., Bellibaş, M. Ş., Esen, M., & Gümüş, E. (2021). A systematic review of studies on leadership models in educational research. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(1), 25–48.
5. Hallinger, P. (1996). Leadership for school restructuring. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 32(4), 498–518.
6. Hallinger, P. (2011). Leadership for learning: Lessons from 40 years of empirical research. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 49(2), 125–142.
7. International Labour Organization. (2018). *World Employment and Social Outlook 2018: Greening with Jobs*. Geneva: ILO, 182 p. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_628654.pdf
8. Jackson, D., & Tomlinson, M. (2020). Investigating the relationship between leadership, employability, and organizational outcomes. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 39(3), 523–536.
9. Kim, T., & Lee, Y. (2020). Principal instructional leadership for teacher participation in professional learning communities: Evidence from Korea. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(4), 697–717.
10. Lapina, I., Kairiša, I., & Aramina, D. (2015). Role of organizational culture in the quality management of university. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 770–774.
11. Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2020). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership revisited. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(1), 5–22.
12. Liu, S., & Hallinger, P. (2018). Principal instructional leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and teacher professional learning in China. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 54(4), 501–528.

13. O'Reilly, C. A., & Chatman, J. A. (1996). Culture as social control: Corporations, cults, and commitment. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 18, 157–200.
14. Schein, E. H. (1996). Culture: The missing concept in organization studies. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 41(2), 229–240.
15. Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass.

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Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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2026. № 1

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Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
